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Commercialization and culture in Australian gambling

Abstract

Gambling has a prominent place in Australian culture. Following the liberalization of commercial gambling in the 1970s, Australia entered into an intensive phase of industrializing gambling as a form of mass entertainment and a significant source of public revenue and private profit. An important part of the industrialization of gambling has been technological transformation, which has made possible the production and distribution of new and enhanced gambling commodities. Knowledgeable actors in betting markets have always been required to adapt themselves to contingencies in assessing risks. These contingencies now include those that arise from institutional arrangements designed to protect commercial house advantage or provide credible gambling products to a mass market. This paper analyses the example of controversy surrounding betting on AFL matches, to shed light on dynamic interactions between gambling consumption, the introduction of technology and gambling commodities, and the culture of the game.

As the legend goes, Australians will gamble on anything. As Peter Charlton (1987) captured in the title of his book on the subject, even 'two flies up a wall'. According to this way of thinking, there is something of an 'elective affinity' between the Australian character and gambling. Perhaps this is related to the conditions encountered by the British colonists, with the post-1788 history of Australia being replete with stories of hardship and danger, stories that seemingly turn on nothing more than 'blind luck'. An interpretation of the Australian passion for gambling as being formed via a particular experience of contingency, based in the pragmatics of struggle, situates the culture of gambling in Australia in a specific socio-historical context. This contextualization contrasts with a relatively intellectual or spiritual apprehension of the role of number and luck in deep structures of fortune and fate, as found in Chinese culture for example (Basu 1991).

If there is something in the legend of a particularly 'Australian' attachment to gambling, it is refracted through different social and cultural prisms (McMillen 1996). As John O'Hara (1988) has argued, the stories of early Australian gambling cultures are tied up with the construction of working-class experience in Australia's young cities. This experience was not always legitimate, or viewed as desirable. The 'right' to gamble was won in the colonies despite strong religious opposition to a practice construed as a vice or moral affliction (O'Hara 1988). The importance of working-class male experience to the flourishing of gambling continued to be important after the Second World War, particularly as the poker machine industry emerged in New South Wales (Lynch 1990). However, after 1956, when the NSW club sector began to legitimately operate poker machines, gambling also became available for women, and slowly grew more socially acceptable.

The period of Australia's gambling history of interest here is the phase of liberalization and expansion of commercial gambling, which accelerated from the 1970s. There were two main aspects of this expansion. State and territory governments licensed and continue to control casinos. In the 1990s, poker machines were introduced to pubs and/or clubs in all

parts of the country except Western Australia. This proved to be somewhat fortuitous timing – the emergence of commercialized gambling as a multi-billion dollar industry coincided with almost two decades of uninterrupted economic growth and rising personal and household wealth. Commercialized gambling was thus able to situate itself as a form of leisure and entertainment available to citizens of an affluent society. However, at the same time this society also became more complex, with a diverse multicultural nation emerging. The intersection of differing cultural values and practices with the flourishing opportunities to bet thus became part of the Australian gambling landscape. In turn, more attention also started to be paid to relationships between more traditional forms of indigenous gambling (Brady 2004) and the emergence of commercial gambling industries in places like the Northern Territory and other regions of northern Australia (Young et al. 2007).

The forging of governable and taxable spaces for the activities of commercial actors is the point, I would argue, where we can start to talk of the emergence of cultures of gambling consumption. It is at this point that cultures of audit and standardization start to be applied to gambling commodities, ensuring levels of accountability and consumer fairness, and securing streams of government revenue. It is tempting to see such developments as simply an efficient means of extending participation in, and hence profiting from, socially embedded gambling forms such as horse racing. It is also tempting to view contemporary gambling consumption as a predominantly straightforward exchange of money for entertainment, with the ‘interest’ of gaining a windfall from gambling merely one of the attractions of this form of leisure. However, in this article I will emphasize a particular form of interaction within popular contemporary commercial gambling contexts. This is the interaction between knowledgeable and interested gambling actors and the various forms adopted by powerful commercial systems to manufacture and sell gambling commodities. I will suggest that the dialogic and interactive relationship between innovative commercial systems and gambling consumers has a profound influence on the instituting of cultures of gambling consumption. Commercial relationships and the industrial dynamics of rationalization, technological advance and commodity enhancement operate to reorder gambling culture to some extent. As we will see, this reordering may even spill over into the culture of the game.

It is not so much the decline of socially embedded cultures of gambling, such as that surrounding horse racing, that I want to describe (if indeed such a decline can be said to be taking place). Rather, I want to focus on the way gambling business and government regulation frame contemporary experiences and understandings of gambling as forms of mass consumption, but without eliminating homo aleator from the equation. The phenomenon of industrialized consumption of gambling products has seen gambling expenditure (losses) escalate to around A\$15 billion annually. The relationships between this culture of mass consumption and socially embedded cultures of knowledgeable gambling are complex and as yet quite opaque. However, relatively well-informed gambling actors continue to operate in a variety of contemporary commercial gambling contexts. These actors must deploy knowledge and strategy in adapting to the dynamics of commercial systems that stage and frame gambling markets.

The paper proceeds by first briefly defining industrialized and commercialized gambling, and the framing of markets for the mass consumption of gambling products. Examples of processes of adaptation by participants in three gambling consumption contexts are

briefly outlined to give an idea of the diversity of spaces of gambling consumption. The main body of the paper then considers one example in more depth: the framing of sportsbetting markets for Australian Football League (AFL) matches.

In particular, it looks at circumstances in pre-season and late regular season matches that call into question the integrity of the gambling product being offered to consumers, at least in the way it is theoretically framed. The case shows how the logics of commercial gambling and of football management can come into conflict. The discussion then highlights how knowledgeable actors are in a position to appreciate certain 'externalities' that might be influencing betting behaviour and markets. The concluding discussion draws on these examples to argue that the interaction of powerful commercial systems and knowledgeable actors is a key dynamic in contemporary cultures of gambling consumption. I finish by speculating that this dynamic will continue to shape transformations in gambling and its framing in social and cultural contexts.

Commercial systems, culture(s) of gambling consumption and adaptation

Western commercialized and industrialized gambling is perhaps best defined by Reith (1999, 1) as an activity that is 'strictly demarcated from the everyday world around it and within which chance is deliberately courted as a mechanism which governs a redistribution of wealth among players and a commercial interest or "house"'. The setting of rules and regulations, and the calibrating of technologies, govern the precise specification of 'house' advantage. The setting up of 'house' interests via the liberalizing of commercial gambling markets in Australian states and territories has been a form of coordinated economic action undertaken by coalitions of governments, state agencies, and corporate and other private-sector organizations (Livingstone and Woolley 2007). The introduction of casinos, hotel and club poker machine gambling and sportsbetting (including betting on virtually any independent third-party event such as elections) has achieved its aim of facilitating significant redistributions of wealth (stakes) as witnessed by burgeoning private profits and public revenues.

In Australia, the most recent survey (June 2005) showed a total of 5370 businesses involved in providing gambling, of which 77.8% were clubs, pubs, taverns and bars (ABS 2006, 5). In total consumption terms, commercial gambling expenditure was \$16,910.3 million in 2004–2005. This equated to 3.05% of household disposable income that year. The dominant market was poker machine gambling in clubs and hotels, which accounted for 59.7% (\$10,095.5 million) of total expenditure (gambler losses), compared with casinos (15.6%, or \$2638.5 million), off-course wagering on racing (TAB) (11.5%, or \$1936.5 million) and lotteries (9.6%, or \$1619.1 million) (OESR 2006). State and territory governments received \$4772 million in taxation revenue from gambling in 2006–2007, of which \$2958 million came from poker machine gambling in clubs and hotels (ABS 2008).

The rapid institution of commercial activity at this scale requires substantial investment, pre-existing infrastructure such as telecommunications networks, and significant research and development (R&D) of technically based commodity forms around which transaction chains can be organized. At the same time, a regulatory regime, consisting of licensing processes, monitoring and auditing practices, and industry product standards, is required. Relatively new gambling sectors such as online sportsbetting are introduced 'off the shelf' through coordinated commercial and governmental action. Older sectors such as horse and dog race wagering have evolved more organically, from face-to-face

interactions at racetracks and illegal off-course starting price (SP) bookmakers through a range of technical platforms that have changed the culture of wagering (e.g. the emergence of off-course totalisator wagering that eliminated the SP bookies). The advent of the Internet has provided a new medium for the sale of 'older' gambling products, while encouraging innovation in the product offerings available. Racing has adopted networked computerised information technology (CIT) based infrastructure over the past two decades, enabling expansion of both the channels of product delivery and the commodity forms that can be sold. For example, totalisator agencies now sell lottery-style 'quick pick' wagering products, with the selections of numbers (horses) done by random number generators (RNGs).

Variations in the evolution of gambling forms are of interest in and of themselves; however, the purpose of this brief outline is really to make one simple point: that powerful commercial systems have been put in place to enable gambling commodities to be staged for sale to an expanded market of ordinary consumers and committed gamblers alike. The regulatory, commercial and technical staging of gambling products for sale constitutes what I shall refer to as the 'framing' of gambling markets (Callon 1998). The process of framing creates spaces for new or transformed cultures of consumption of gambling products to emerge.

The framing of spaces of consumption of gambling is thus as diverse as gambling forms themselves. Hence quite varied processes of adaptation and learning can evolve in practice within them. Before going on to a detailed case study from the field of sportsbetting, I will first illustrate something of this variation via brief descriptions of two quite different framings of gambling activity, and of the kinds of adaptations that can emerge and evolve within these spaces of participation and consumption. The first example is the playing of the card game poker against other gamblers via online gambling websites. This form of gambling has become very popular throughout the world as part of the Internet revolution, while poker itself has developed something of a cult status in recent years, with competitions televised and local 'tournaments' being popular in Australian hotels and clubs. The online game is played in a virtual room in which remotely located gamblers compete against each other. However, what separates poker conducted around a table and that played via the Internet is the use of technical prostheses to assist play. Online poker players routinely use 'bots', small applications that monitor the betting behaviour of their competitors, to assist their gambling strategy. A gambler playing with the assistance of a 'bot' will know the betting patterns of others around the virtual table – for example, how aggressively they tend to bet the relative strength of their revealed hands. This creates an advantage for the 'bot'-assisted gambler, who can consider the behaviour of an opponent on a current hand in comparison to their historical pattern. These data add a stream of systematic information to their betting strategy.

The online poker player who uses a 'bot' thus has certain informational advantages over those who do not use this form of technical prosthesis to enhance their calculations. However, what has tended to occur in online poker games has been the adoption of 'bots' by the vast majority of players, particularly those who play seriously and/or regularly. In the absence of one form of information about an opponent – that is, their physical appearance, mannerisms or apparent emotional responses – online poker players substitute a system of data collection and processing that illuminates opponents' behaviour. The suspected use of 'bots' by most or all online poker players leads gamblers

to adapt their behaviour to incorporate the role of 'bots' in the game strategy. For example, as one gambler described it, you have to be aware that some players will gamble in a seemingly reckless way on several hands in which they do not have good cards to disguise the situation when they do have good cards and want to bet big. These gamblers are playing to their opponents' 'bots', signalling through the historical data that are being compiled and interpreted about their behaviour that they do not need to have really good cards to significantly increase the size of their bets. The hope is to lull their opponents into thinking this is their typical pattern, making them more likely to take greater risks against this player on the occasions when the cards really have fallen their way. The knowledgeable agents of online poker games have thus had to adapt their strategizing to incorporate the capabilities of technical enhancements to individual poker-playing skills. This highlights the way in which the conduct of a particular game can be altered by technology and the qualities of the commercial system staging the gambling product. In this case, once the medium of the game is digital, new strategies and capabilities also come to the fore that transform gamblers' behaviour.

Technology is also important in the interactive relationship between poker machines and gamblers. Poker machine technology is big business, servicing a multi-billion dollar consumption sector in Australia. Innovation in the design and manufacture of poker machines is designed to extend the amount of time and money spent gambling. Extending gamblers' time on device (TOD) and the revenue returned per available customer (RevPAC) requires an engineering solution that is entertaining and satisfying in relation to the rate at which financial losses occur. The knowledge inputs that underpin poker machine technologies approach this task via two related strands of human science research. The first uses principles of behavioural psychology (Skinner 1953), in which the redistribution of gamblers' stakes as wins and losses occurs in such a way as to operate as a random ratio reinforcement schedule, disguising losses through the intermittent experience of machine events including wins, bonus features and free games. The second strand of research uses cognitive science to create the illusion of increased chances to win – for example by regularly featuring winning symbols (near-misses) or providing multiple lines to enable simultaneous bets and the illusion of more chances to win.

The capabilities, features and attractions of poker machine technology are not static, but rather are the outcome of processes of industrial R&D1 and incremental innovation that lead to 'new' product offerings. The interactive relationship between poker machine technology and gamblers is thus always evolving. The strategies that gamblers adopt, despite the random nature of poker machines that means gamblers cannot influence game outcomes, are thus formatted and transformed by changes in the game technology. While it has been shown that many poker machine gamblers do not really understand that the outcomes of the game are entirely beyond their control (Productivity Commission 1999), it is important to realize that the play of all poker machine gamblers is to some extent configured in the interactive relationship with technology. While poker machines are not games of skill, the forms of behaviour and actions required by the obdurate materiality of poker machine technology provide the experience of interactive agency that engages gamblers in the activity. While contemporary poker machine gamblers who touch the screens and push the buttons on current networked CIT devices share a fundamental experience with those who pulled the handle of the old mechanical steppers that have now vanished from the market, the profusion of winning possibilities, game options and forms of reinforcement has led to an intensification of the interactive agency of poker

machine gamblers. The relatively high level of consumption of poker machine gambling in contemporary Australia therefore cannot be understood adequately without taking into account this transformation of technology and the adaptation of gamblers to the experiential possibilities the advances in technology have presented.

The interactions between commercial systems and consumers in the two examples described are both technologically mediated. In the case of online poker, the adaptive behaviour of gambler is framed cognitively in terms of strategy and reflexivity. In the case of poker machine gamblers, adaptation to the commercial system is more practice based, with gambling behaviour incrementally reformatted over time by the new betting options and game features presented. To highlight the diverse 'framing' of gambling markets, I want to contrast these forms of adaptation with that of gamblers who bet on the outcome of AFL matches. In particular, I want to highlight the way in which these gamblers need to strategize in terms of seemingly 'external' factors, namely aspects of competition rules and logics of football management, which are not proper to the isolated sporting contest upon which bets are actually made, but rather are aspects of the institutional and commercial contexts that frame these contests and the AFL competition as a whole.

Gambling on AFL football

In 2005, the Australian Football League (AFL), responsible for the administration of the national Australian Rules Football competition (also known as the AFL), entered into commercial arrangements with the Melbourne-based Australian stock exchange-listed gambling company Tabcorp and the London-based betting exchange Betfair to provide betting services on its official competition matches. The agreements were for five years and gave the two companies exclusive rights to provide betting services on AFL-sanctioned matches in exchange for an annual fee estimated at around \$1 million dollars for each company. The companies are also entitled to use the AFL brand in their marketing.

A range of betting options is now provided by the two companies – for example, on leading individual awards and end-of-season finishing order of the 16 AFL clubs. The major betting opportunities, however, are based on the outcomes and margins of the eight matches staged in each of the 22 rounds of the regular season, the nine matches of the finals series, and the pre-season knockout competition conducted in the month preceding the regular season, which commences in late April. Tabcorp offers totalisator and fixed odds betting products, with totalisator bets entitling the holder to a proportional share of the total prize pool depending on the size of their wager relative to all those who made the correct selection. Betfair is a betting exchange, which matches the bets offered by clients with willing counterparties, enabling their clients to bet directly against each other while the company receives a commission for providing the 'matching' service. Large volumes of betting on AFL matches are also conducted via sportsbetting companies licensed and operated in the Northern Territory, via online and telephone accounts.

Interestingly, the AFL's commercial agreements with Tabcorp and Betfair are described as 'partnerships' or 'product and integrity arrangements'. The basis of these partnerships is a mutual recognition of the importance of the integrity of the product being offered. In other words, the independent third-party event (the football match) is considered to be of reduced value to both the AFL and the betting agencies if the integrity of outcomes is perceived to be corrupted or vulnerable to corruption. A crucial part of the commercial

partnerships is thus an arrangement whereby the betting companies provide client data to the AFL, enabling the AFL to monitor participation in gambling on its sanctioned games.

The AFL gambling policy restricts footballers or other AFL employees from directly or indirectly betting on AFL-sanctioned matches or events contained in these matches. It is also contrary to the policy to assist others to gamble or to disclose information about players, tactics or other matters that are not already in the public domain. The key measure of the AFL gambling policy is thus to ensure the perception of credibly independent match outcomes by preventing footballers or other participants in the staging of its sanctioned matches from being involved in any way in betting markets staged on the outcomes of these matches. Since these arrangements were put in place, several AFL players, and at least one board member of an AFL club, have been sanctioned or warned for betting on AFL matches in contravention of the policy.

The integrity arrangements built into gambling business agreements are thus designed to frame the outcome of matches as depending entirely on proper 'footballing' factors. From the gambler's perspective, the equation is designed to be simple: which team is more likely to win and by how much? Football factors, which I will conceptualize as 'internal' to the framing of the market on a particular match, include home ground advantage, head-to-head records, weather or ground conditions and the selected teams of the opposing clubs. These variables can fluctuate considerably (e.g. dry or wet conditions) but can be known by all. Internal factors, such as perceptions of home ground advantage, have been found to impact on aggregate betting strategies in some circumstances (Schnytzer and Weinberg 2008).

Information about these 'internal' variables is thus fundamental to assessments of risk and to formulation of betting strategies. In recent years, the AFL has taken measures to enhance the reliability of such information. For example, the AFL limited the discretion of football clubs to change selected players at the last minute, or at least to ensure greater transparency about the 'odds' of particular players being able to participate. This may be due to the perceived disproportionate influence 'star' players can have on the outcome of matches. Sanctions for withdrawals of players after a certain deadline were introduced in an attempt to make the practice less attractive to clubs. While nominating a star player unlikely to play can have an influence on the way opposition teams may plan for the game, it also can affect the decision making of gamblers. The changes to team nomination procedures instigated by the AFL had the effect of standardizing the information available to football gamblers, regardless of whether or not this was directly intended as an 'integrity' measure in relation to gambling. Taking all this information into account, football betting should thus be a simple equation for gamblers: allocate relative significance to 'football factors' and make a reasoned decision. This process, however, leaves one further assumption unchallenged: that both teams are equally 'willing' to win.

AFL gambling controversies: Inside and outside the frame

But do AFL teams always have an equal 'interest' in winning? What external factors might contribute to an asymmetry in the distribution of 'willingness' to win a match without it destroying the 'integrity' of the product? And what kinds of information and calculations are required in these circumstances, such that a gambler might be considered a knowledgeable actor? And finally, what kinds of information sources might be most helpful in aiding gamblers adapt to contexts involving variables that, de jure, do not exist,

having been helpfully bracketed out via 'product and integrity arrangements' and the AFL's rules and regulations?

Two controversies stand out in relation to gambling on AFL matches. The first is betting on the pre-season competition, which is sanctioned by the AFL and therefore framed as having 'integrity' from the gambling perspective. According to a football management logic, the value of the pre-season competition often lies elsewhere than in winning matches or the competition. Many coaches seem to value more highly the provision of competitive practice matches and an opportunity for tactical testing, for example. The second controversy relates to the structure of the AFL's National Draft system, whereby outstanding young talents are distributed to AFL clubs by virtue of a series of 'picks', starting from the club that finished last and proceeding in order to the winner of the AFL Premiership. The controversy here lies in the Draft's relation to what is colloquially known as 'tanking'. Tanking refers to circumstances where teams that have lost the chance for real success part-way through a season are perceived to be content to 'bottom out' so as to secure the best selections from the following year's Draft. I will discuss each of these controversies in turn, with a view to shedding some light on the questions posed above.

The AFL pre-season competition is a knockout competition, commencing in early February and finishing in late March, with the final played two weeks prior to the start of the premiership season proper. From a marketing point of view, the competition is important in building interest in the season ahead, and for the clubs that contest the final there is the excitement of a minor trophy, which can also have knock-on financial benefits in terms of boosting memberships and sponsorships. However, such benefits must be weighed against key football management objectives, such as having players fit and fresh for the long season ahead. Prolonged involvement in the pre-season competition increases the risk of untimely injuries and the exacerbation of the general fatigue that is always a factor during the premiership season. Purely 'football' logic, geared towards the objective of success in the September finals series, may imply only limited involvement in the pre-season competition.

Controversy regarding the pre-season competition and the 'rights' of gamblers came to the fore in 2008. In the first round of the competition, the Sydney Swans played Hawthorn at Aurora Stadium in Launceston. With two minutes remaining in the match and Sydney trailing by two points, Sydney coach Paul Roos made a substitution, sending one of his players into the forward line. According to an official overseeing the interchange of players on and off the ground, Roos gave instructions to the player, using words to the effect of 'Go forward, just don't kick a goal'. The official reported Roos' alleged comments to the AFL, which then appointed retired Justice John Winneke to lead an investigation into whether Roos' conduct amounted to 'match-fixing', punishable by a \$100,000 fine and an indefinite suspension.

The CEO of the AFL, Andrew Demetriou, explained the rationale for the case related to its anti-gambling/match-fixing rules. Demetriou was widely quoted in the media on this point, saying that: 'The rules are put in place because there are people who actually bet on these games' (Herald Sun 2008). In turn, Roos called for betting to be banned on pre-season cup games. In describing his bemusement at the charge, he said: 'Andrew [Demetriou] explained it had something to do with the gambling clause, so just trying to get your head around that is a little bit hard . . .'. As Roos, an experienced premiership coach, described it, there was an apparent conflict between the integrity of AFL pre-season matches as

gambling products, and the obligations of coaches. Roos commented: 'I think it's a fine competition to play in . . . but most coaches don't want to compromise their preparation for round one . . . More and more focus is on round one because we're paid to be effective and win games in the regular season' (Tomarchio 2008). Roos became even more explicit in describing a variety of logics underpinning participation in the pre-season competition: 'As long as everyone takes it as what it is – a pre-season competition with everyone having varying degrees of what their outcomes need to be. And it seems more so than ever more coaches are saying, "Well, I'm focused on round one of the regular season"' (emphasis added) (Ormond 2008). In a later statement immediately prior to his investigation hearing, Roos clarified his view of the competition further, stating that 'over the six years that I have been involved with the competition (NAB Cup), we have used it as a feeder competition for our young guys, and we did the same this year' (Herald Sun 2008).

The situation that arose in the Roos match-fixing case was not at all surprising to football aficionados. A trip around some of the football journalism websites and blogs found a range of opinion, but little dissent from the proposition that not all clubs are equally interested in winning the pre-season competition. Many bloggers and commentators were quite clear about the way they constructed their understanding of the controversy: as a conflict between gambling integrity and football management. One could argue that all the gratuitous rule changes for the NAB Cup show that the AFL is not taking the competition entirely seriously either. If they were that invested in credibility they'd use normal rules for the NAB Cup and save the experimental rules for the Regional Challenge.

As far as the gambling issue goes, anyone betting on the Swans to win a pre-season game in 2008 deserves to lose it all. (Posted by Zingiber on 5 March 2008, 9.52 a.m.) I used to reckon Blighty was a genius but now Roosey is . . . how good a coach is he that he can get within two points in a game he is not trying to win! Somebody once told me that jockeys don't always try (not that i believe that) and some have even been suspended for it. I bet they wish they were as clever as Roosey and only lost the race by a short half head instead of being 6 lengths back under a tight hold. Hard to give a bloke time for that. Like I said, genius! (Posted by rocco on 6 March 2008, 3.25 p.m.)

Anyone who would bet on the NAB cup should seriously consider seeking gambling counselling. (Posted by Psi on 6 March 2008, 8.20 a.m.). Football journalists are no less circumspect in their assessment of the objectives of clubs in the pre-season cup. In an article from 2006, entitled 'Clubs Don't Care About Cup', Michael Horan described the mood in AFL clubs as follows: 'While every AFL coach who straps on a clipboard wants to win, there is no doubt winning isn't everything in February.' He went on to state that 'most fans understand and accept' this situation. Interestingly, Paul Roos featured amongst those quoted by the article, some two years prior to his eventual 'trial', saying: 'Our goal is to prepare for round one and to give our younger players an opportunity to play against some quality opposition.' Despite the Sydney Swans being the 2005 AFL Premiers, bookmakers rated them as rank outsiders at \$41 to win the 2006 pre-season competition. It would seem that bookmakers were therefore 'pricing in' certain externalities relating specifically to the pre-season cup and the relative 'willingness' of clubs to win matches.

The AFL investigation of the 2008 controversy found that Roos' comments did not lead to a conclusion that Roos had intentionally induced or encouraged a player to perform otherwise than on his merits. The AFL's Legal and Business Affairs manager, Andrew Dillon, commented that: 'The integrity of the competition is paramount and the AFL was

obligated to fully investigate the concerns raised by match officials.’ From the perspective of the core constituency of the AFL – football fans, the media and those involved in the clubs themselves – the result was entirely predictable. It appears clearly understood by the Australian Rules ‘community’ that winning is not the priority of many, if not most, clubs involved in pre-season matches. The pre-season has a particular place in football culture and, as the comments above reflect, there is little sympathy for those betting on the outcomes without an understanding of this broader context.

In fact, the AFL’s assertion of the rights of gamblers to ‘product integrity’ as equivalent to the imperatives of those involved in football management were not viewed kindly by many insiders. These views were articulated by champion ex-player and then Brisbane Lions coach Leigh Matthews a month after the Roos investigation, which he described as ridiculous. Matthews’ opinion on the situation was widely quoted: ‘I think the AFL should say, “You want to bet on the footy fine, don’t include us. Don’t ask us to have rules and regulations that pander to people who might want to bet on the game.”’ Matthews said he ‘hated’ the perception that imperatives arising from involvement in commercial gambling arrangements were a factor in the way football was run: ‘The one thing that really annoys me is any thought that whatever we do as a game has something to do with people betting on it.’

The AFL’s response to Matthews was to point out that its gambling integrity partnerships enabled it to monitor gambling on football. In this, the AFL might be accused of being a trifle disingenuous. Whilst no one ‘inside’ football culture seemed to be criticizing the procedures to monitor corruption through betting on football, an underlying resentment seemed to be expressed by Matthews, which was more to do with the corruption of football culture, broadly understood. Specifically in this case, dissatisfaction appeared to lie with the subjecting of the accepted function of the pre-season to criteria imposed by the framing of the competition as a gambling market. What Matthews, Roos, fans, journalists and other ‘insiders’ really seemed to be saying was that the AFL’s investigation was largely rhetorical, designed to conceal the acknowledged asymmetry that exists in the willingness to win pre-season games. The AFL’s interest in so doing appeared to be widely perceived as attempting to shore up the credibility of the gambling product, potentially at the expense of traditional football culture.

A second controversy surrounding gambling on AFL-sanctioned matches, which relates to the National Draft system of allocating new players to clubs, has become an annual site of conspiracy theories and intrigue which, whether or not ‘real’, has concrete repercussions for betting markets and gambling behaviour. The AFL National Draft is conducted in reverse of the finishing order of the previous premiership season, with the last-placed club having first choice amongst the new draftees and so on. In recent years, clubs that have won fewer than five games for two successive seasons have also been eligible for a priority pick of the draftees, a pick that occurs before all others. So, for example, although Richmond Football Club finished last in season 2007, its first pick of the Draft actually occurred after the priority pick ‘earned’ by Carlton Football Club, which finished above Richmond but had won fewer than five games in 2006 and 2007. The controversy associated with access to the player Draft is known colloquially as ‘tanking’, which can be summarized as endeavouring not to win too many games, either relative to other clubs or to thresholds for priority picks, such that opportunities to profit from the Draft would be reduced for little apparent gain.

Tanking is considered by AFL watchers to be more subtle than merely 'trying to lose'. This is because football management strategies focused on longer term outcomes may nevertheless influence short-term results. All AFL clubs have a limited number of players permitted on their 'playing list', so strategies to shape the list are strategic and medium term. List management is thus an important part of clubs' longer term performance objectives. Where a club looks unlikely to participate in the finals series in a particular season, list management decisions such as sending star players for rehabilitating surgery or bleeding young players to accelerate the gaining of experience, coupled with match-day experimenting with player positioning or team tactics, are arguably sound longer term football management strategies. These list management and game-day decisions may therefore be beneficial to the future of the club, but have short-term costs in terms of match results. List management 'tanking' over time, so the theory goes, may also bring the indirect benefit of earlier selections in the National Draft than would otherwise have occurred. Tanking by deliberately 'throwing' matches is thus not considered to be the key element of the tanking controversy.

'Tanking' is also a mediatized phenomenon. For example, following a disappointing first half of the season, Port Adelaide coach Mark Williams described his strategy for the remainder of 2008 as 'picking for the future', leading to headlines that he had 'admitted' to tanking. Various ex-players and officials have described the list management practices of their own or other clubs as effectively 'tanking the season', with some saying that it was difficult to argue that winning was in the best interests of clubs at certain times. One former AFL player and senior coach summarized tanking as a structural problem that arises by mid-season every year:

How times have changed. Where once teams had been highly motivated to avoid the ignominy of the wooden spoon, now we have a system that makes it a tantalising object of desire. By the mid-season break the 16 teams that start the season full of anticipation and excitement become more like 10 to 12 that still have finals hopes. Four to six teams already have made a decision they cannot make the finals, so are duty bound to look after the best interests of their club. They effectively have 'put the flag up'. That can only mean the draft for the following season and this is where a problem is emerging. Clubs are tanking the season (Thomas 2007).

The continual discussion and debate about 'tanking' in the media is also important in relation to the 'credibility' of AFL-sanctioned matches. One 2008 AFL coach described 'tanking' as a 'slur' on the game. Another described the perception of tanking as itself a matter of concern for the AFL administrators: Whether there is tanking or not, and I don't think anyone can really assess that, I don't think it's that clear-cut, I think it's more a perception. And if the perception's out there . . . you'd certainly think the AFL could probably look at it. (The Age 2008). The widely perceived and mediatized controversy over 'tanking', mythical or otherwise, can be considered an epiphenomenon of institutional policies and regulations that are nominally 'external' to the outcomes of sanctioned AFL matches. The National Draft is designed to create a process which, all other things being equal, would lead to an even distribution of playing talent and hence on-field success. This is far from the reality, of course, but 'tanking' refers to the perception that seeking to accelerate the process of performance decline, and thereby the harvesting of new talent, can lead to a more rapid rejuvenation of on-field fortunes than would otherwise have occurred. Cases cited in support of this argument include St Kilda and Hawthorn, which

both 'bottomed out' and drafted large numbers of highly regarded playing talent. Hawthorn rebounded from 15th in 2004 and 14th in 2005 to Premiers in 2008, largely due to wise selections using early selections among Draft talent. St Kilda went from last in 2000 and second last in 2002 to top four finishes in the period 2004–2006, but, unlike Hawthorn, is widely perceived to have 'missed the window of opportunity' created by its prior 'bottoming out'.

There is no evidence that Draft considerations alter the probabilities of struggling clubs winning matches (Borland 2006). However, real or imagined, tanking does create controversy around betting on AFL matches. Late in the season in particular, gamblers who bet 'objectively' on factors 'inside' the frame of the AFL betting product – that is, without knowledge of the draft system and its implications – would seem to be at a disadvantage. This is perhaps best illustrated through an example. The final regular season round of 2007 featured a match between the 14th-placed (of 16) Melbourne Football Club and the 15th-placed Carlton Football Club. Despite a series of objective football factors – the clubs were closely matched in overall performance; Melbourne were missing several key players; Melbourne had suffered several heavy losses in recent matches – that would normally indicate both clubs had a reasonable chance of winning the match, bookmakers set opening prices that suggested this was not the case. A rough survey of the prices being offered by bookmakers on the match showed Melbourne at around \$1.25 and Carlton at more than \$3.00.

The unusual calculation of these odds was well understood in football circles and prominent in the print and television media. One bookmaker was widely reported as delaying the setting of odds on the game and handling it with 'absolute kid gloves'. As this bookmaker saw it: 'The odds should be a lot closer than what they are but because of the widespread talk about Carlton wanting to lose they're not' (The Age 2007). Another bookmaker reported taking bets of \$20,000 on the match, stating this was far more than was usual for a 'dead rubber' at the end of the season. Carlton had won just four matches in 2006 and only another four up to the final game of 2007. If the team lost, it 'earned' a priority pick to be taken before all others in the National Draft; along with its pick for finishing 15th, it would effectively have picks one and three. Alternatively, if the team won, Carlton would end up with only the third pick overall. Melbourne had also only won four matches in 2007 prior to the last round, and by losing stood to 'earn' a priority pick at the start of the second round of the draft, in effect pick number 17. Both teams appeared to have far more to gain by losing than by winning this otherwise meaningless match. As one political journalist described it: 'All that has to happen now is for Melbourne and Carlton to somehow find a credible way not to win' (Happell 2007).

In the end, Carlton lost the game and benefited from first and third picks in the 2007 National Draft. Early in 2008, a former Carlton assistant coach, Tony Liberatore, who had been part of the match-day coaching team at Carlton for 2007, including the final match, discussed the tanking issue on Channel Nine's *The Footy Show*. In the course of this discussion, Liberatore said that winning matches 'wasn't the be all and end all'. Describing the match-day situation, he said that he had 'never heard [a directive to lose], but I could feel it, if that makes sense. Nobody ever said we're not going to win but the feeling in the group was that it was a bit of a laugh' (ABC 2008). The AFL voiced concern about the statements, but after meeting with Liberatore terminated any further investigation of the matter.

Conclusion

The AFL's commercial partnerships with gambling companies oblige it to deploy a variety of strategies to ensure the integrity of its sanctioned matches as betting products. Despite such strategies, the perception that tanking occurs in the AFL has implications for gamblers and gambling providers, altering the behaviour found in betting markets. The cultural knowledge and adaptive behaviour of bookmakers and punters are crucial to the functioning of these markets. As we have seen, bookmakers do not set odds on matches solely on the basis of the framing imposed by the AFL, which would mandate a symmetrical distribution of willingness to win a particular match. Rather, bookmakers 'price in' a range of 'externalities'.

In the case of 'tanking', this means precisely the perception that there is an asymmetric distribution of willingness to win, due to the influence of the National Draft process. Viewed from inside the frame, the integrity of gambling on third-party events such as sporting competitions largely depends on the soundness of the information provided. However, gamblers who rely on such 'objective' information streams would appear to be at a disadvantage compared with those who have 'grassroots' knowledge of sports cultures and institutional factors that, nominally at least, are bracketed off from game outcomes. Knowledgeable gamblers in such circumstances are those who understand the contextual factors that need to be dragged into the frame, alongside results, players, form, and so on, and can therefore understand both the externalities that bookmakers are 'pricing in' and whether the prices they set in response to this wider set of factors represent an attractive premium on the risks associated with betting on such controversial matches.

As we have seen by looking at gambling controversies surrounding pre-season and late-season games in AFL-sanctioned competitions, such cultural knowledge is invaluable, with a range of informal information sources, such as blogs, Internet forums and the mainstream media constituting important resources. Of course, without the appropriate prior processes of acculturation, sifting through informal and mediatized representations of likely future risk events is likely to be as confusing as it is enlightening. Insiders, embedded as they are in cultural contexts, are much more likely to be able to navigate the complexity of gambling markets such as that for Australian Rules Football. Such adaptive behaviour among gamblers is, in itself, not new. However, what the example discussed highlights is that the commercial arrangements that frame sports competitions as gambling markets do not prevent the spillover of factors that were intended to be excluded from the gambling space. The ongoing evolution of gambling culture thus includes adapting to interactions shaped by powerful commercial actors and systems, both from inside and outside the frame.

In conclusion, the commercial liberalization and industrialization of gambling underpins a dynamic of innovation, ensuring the emergence of new products and forms of staging and delivering gambling commodities to consumers. Commercial gambling, whether playing cards online, interacting with new poker machine technologies or grappling with the imposed framing of sports betting, changes gambling culture. Sometimes change is quite incremental and at other times quite dramatic and radical, as we have seen with the emergence of CITs and networked forms. However, as we have also seen, gamblers and embedded gambling cultures are knowledgeable, resilient and adaptable. In Australia, contemporary cultures of gambling consumption are emerging via dynamic relationships between commercial and institutional actors, knowledgeable gamblers with their

accumulated cultural resources and broader pools of consumers. This process is never static or complete; rather, the flow of innovation and adaptation in gambling is restless, ceaseless and transforming. The qualities of gambling commodities and gamblers' experiences on offer today are not necessarily those that will characterize tomorrow.

Notes

1. Aristocrat P/L reported spending A\$104.2 million on R&D in 2006–2007.
2. Comments posted on <http://blogs.theage.com.au/realfooty> in response to the unattributed article entitled 'Credibility and the Cup'.

References

- ABC (Australian Broadcasting Commission). 2008. Liberators to meet with AFL over tanking claims. Unattributed article. 14 March. <http://www.abc.net.au>
- ABS (Australian Bureau of Statistics). 2006. Gambling services. Cat. no. 8684.0. <http://www.abs.gov.au>
- . 2008. Taxation revenue Australia 2006–07. Cat. no. 5506.0. <http://www.abs.gov.au>
- The Age. 2007. AFL bookies react to tanking debate. Unattributed article. 28 August. <http://www.theage.com.au>
- . 2008. Eade joins call for AFL tanking action. Unattributed article. 18 June. <http://www.theage.com.au>
- Basu, E.O. 1991. Profit loss and fate: The entrepreneurial ethic and the practice of gambling in an overseas Chinese community. *Modern China* 17, no. 2: 227–59.
- Borland, J. 2006. Economic design and professional sporting competitions. *Australian Economic Review* 39, no. 4: 439–41.
- Brady, M. 2004. Regulating social problems: The pokies, the Productivity Commission and an Aboriginal community. CAEPR Discussion Paper no. 269. Canberra: Centre for Aboriginal Economic Policy Research, Australian National University.
- Callon, M. 1998. An essay on framing and overflowing: Economic externalities revisited by sociology. In *The laws of the markets*, ed. M. Callon, 244–69. Oxford: Blackwell.
- Charlton, P. 1987. *Two flies up a wall: The Australian passion for gambling*. Sydney: Methuen Haynes.
- Happell, C. 2007. Still plenty in the tank for AFL losers. 27 August. <http://www.crikey.com.au>
- Herald Sun. 2008. Paul Roos would like to see pre-season cup betting banned. Unattributed article. 5 March. <http://www.news.com.au/heraldsun>
- Horan, M. 2006. Clubs don't care about the cup. *Herald Sun*, 23 February.

- Livingstone, C., and R. Woolley. 2007. Risky business: A few provocations on the regulation of electronic gaming machines. *International Gambling Studies* 7, no. 3: 343–58.
- Lynch, R. 1990. Working class luck and vocabularies of hope among regular players of the poker machines. In *Sport and leisure: Trends in Australian popular culture*, ed. D. Rowe and G. Lawrence, 156–78. Sydney: Harcourt Brace Jovanovich.
- McMillen, J., ed. 1996. *Gambling cultures: Studies in history and interpretation*. London: Routledge.
- O'Hara, J. 1988. *A mug's game: A history of gaming and betting in Australia*. Sydney: University of New South Wales Press.
- OESR (Office of Economic and Statistical Research). 2006. *Australian gambling statistics 2005–06*. Brisbane: OESR.
- Ormond, A. 2008. Ban Cup betting: Roos. 4 March. <http://afl.com.au>
- Productivity Commission. 1999. *Australia's gambling industries*. 3 vols. Canberra: Ausinfo.
- Reith, G. 1999. *The age of chance: Gambling in Western culture*. London: Routledge.
- Schnytzer, A., and G. Weinberg. 2008. Testing for home team and favorite biases in the Australian Rules Football fixed-odds and point spread betting markets. *Journal of Sports Economics* 9, no. 2: 173–90.
- Skinner, B.F. 1953. *Science and human behaviour*. New York: Free Press.
- Thomas, G. 2007. Tank is weapon of choice in basement battle. 8 July. <http://www.realfooty.com.au>
- Tomarchio, C. 2008. Paul Roos to face AFL investigation. 4 March. <http://news.theage.com.au>
- Young, M., T. Barnes, M. Stevens, M. Paterson, and M. Morris. 2007. The changing landscape of Indigenous gambling in northern Australia: Current knowledge and future directions. *International Gambling Studies* 7, no. 3: 327–43.